

Disaster Management Network
in the Danube Region

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REPORT: CHALLENGES IN COORDINATION

Work package 5 | Deliverable 2

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The analyses detailed in this report aim to provide a better understanding on the challenges and good practices of the involvement of volunteer organizations in national response systems. We base our findings on structured literature analysis, focus group activities and expert opinion of the authors.

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Executive summary

The analyses detailed in this report aim to provide a better understanding of the challenges and good practices of the involvement of volunteer organizations in national response systems. We base our findings on structured literature analysis, focus group activities and expert opinion of the authors.

The main **challenges in coordination with volunteer and humanitarian organizations** are coming from a large number of actors, their diversity in background and culture, as well as their differences in capacities and competencies. In some cases, this causes inter-organizational mistrust. While roles and competencies remain unclear, actors fail to share information and coordinate their efforts, leading to mismatched responses and duplication of efforts.

To overcome these obstacles, we recommend including volunteer organizations in the planning and preparedness activities to establish pre-agreed procedures. As the number of volunteer organizations is often numerous, we recommend developing a sectoral coordination structure to mitigate the burden of the negotiations needed.

Trust suggested being built during the preparedness phase with regular meetings between volunteer and humanitarian organizations to establish a common understanding of each other's culture, competencies and capacities. This could be strengthened with joint training and exercise activities to gain first-hand experiences. Personal training for volunteers and staff involved in coordination tasks should entail skill development activities covering communication and negotiations as well as cultural awareness. Information management is another focus area to strengthen.

All of these recommendations above highlight the need for the development of regional (and macro-regional) networks, as well as experience and knowledge sharing networks within the disaster management sector.

Introduction

Trained and organizationally embedded disaster volunteers play a crucial role in response and recovery, acting not only just as an additional human asset but as a vital link between the informal resources of the community and the public organizations responding to the event (Britton, 1991). But how can a response system utilize the potential of volunteers? However similar questions have been raised in the '50s and '60s in the United States (see Fritz & Mathewson, 1957; Stoddard, 1969), the challenges of the 21st century and the recent events in Europe elevated the need for better collaboration between public and private actors of disaster management. In this current work, we are focusing on affiliated or trained volunteers (see Britton, 1991), as they are often an integral part of the national and international response structures. Hence, we do not cover the question of spontaneous or convergent volunteers.

1. Figure: humanitarian relationship model. Source: Cozzolino, 2012

In the following, we will focus on Inter-Organizational Coordination, which concerns the coordination between different organizations and their field and headquarters branches. Previous researches identified key challenges as the large number and diversity of organizations involved, the differences of incentives of actors for action, the lack of interoperability related to procedures, tools and methods, as well as the unbalanced allocation of costs, benefits and risks (Salvadó et al., 2015). However the basic relationship model seems to be clear on figure 1, coordination in disaster relief and the humanitarian operations are rather complex in their nature (Cozzolino, 2012). Lack of inter-organizational coordination in disaster scenarios can cause substantial losses of human life and material assets (Kaynak & Tuğer, 2014); therefore, establishing and exercising swift cooperation and coordination structure saves lives.

1. Table: most commonly mentioned challenges and recommended actions

Challenges	Recommendations
a large number of organizations	Creating sectoral coordination structures / clusters.
procedures not interoperable	Pre-agreed procedures in preparedness phase.
different organizational cultures, bias and mistrust	Organizing regular meetings in the preparedness phase to build connections and trust. Joint training and exercise activities, invitations to each other's organizational events.
unclear roles and competences	Organizing regular meetings in the preparedness phase to understand capacities, roles and competencies. Develop pre-agreed share of tasks, response- and contingency plans.
lack of training in coordination	Organize joint training in coordination, as well as skill-developing activities for staff involved in coordination activities (incl. negotiations, communication, cultural awareness, information management, etc.).
lack of information sharing	Encourage the use of existing information-sharing tools. Include information sharing practices between partners in training and exercise activities.
language barriers (for international deployments)	Utilize regional peculiarities (inclusion of native speakers in the teams or as host liaisons). Develop regional dictionaries.
lack of local (municipal) capacity to receive support	Inclusion of "host nation support" into local disaster plans. Prior agreements with possible supporting actors to accommodate outside assistance.
organizational competition (over funds)	Develop joint understanding, goals and code of conduct prior to disasters.

We argue that the obstacles are shown in Table 1 highlight the importance of a holistic approach for preparedness. They also confirm the need for the development of professional and knowledge networks to establish a common understanding and better familiarity between different organizations.

Results of focus groups on volunteer management and host nation support

DiMaND partners organized their second workshop in Dubrovnik, June 29-30. 2021 with a focus on volunteer management and the role of municipalities in Host Nation Support. The details of the event and the discussions are elaborated in the project's deliverable D2.3, we emphasize the results of the focus groups.

During the event, together with an expert of Municipality of Dubrovnik (Mr. Mato Tomljanović), we covered three topics:

- Volunteer organizations in disaster management
- Host Nation Support
- Role of Municipalities in Emergencies

Good practices in volunteer coordination

1. Practices linked between professional and volunteer services
2. Joint training with other volunteer organizations and professionals are very important
3. Centralized volunteer coordination system in case of disasters beneficial
4. Different (specialized) competencies of volunteers are useful
5. Education of volunteers is important so they can enter the organization
6. Alert systems are crucial, but should be reliable
7. Radio communication (reliable without mobile coverage, but should be available for all who are involved), joint channels for on-site commsú
8. Benefits for volunteers (appreciation, motivation – eg. tax exception)

Detected challenges in volunteer coordination

1. Mobilization can be difficult in times (holidays, summertime, work)
2. Membership in multiple volunteer organizations (false statistics, conflicts in mobilization)
3. Specialization (overspecialization)
4. Logistic support and supply
5. Information flow
6. Language barrier

3. Figure: results of group A. Source: DiMaND D2.3

Results of the group discussion strengthen the findings of the literature analysis and the recommendations formed before. The involvement of volunteer organizations is based on a pre-established coordination system, utilizing the specialized competencies of the different partners. Joint training develops shared knowledge and better understanding of each other's capacities, competencies, and procedures, identified as an obstacle prior to this analysis. Individual education of

the volunteers should be the basis of their readiness, which is suggested to include understanding the relevant coordination procedures and systems on their respective level. Item nr. 7. resonates to Eide et al.'s (2013) case study, where authors emphasized the need for a sufficient number of radio equipment across responders, with a shared understanding of transmission procedures and a shared terminology across different emergency services (Eide et al., 2013). Volunteer appreciation is essential to maintain the volunteers' motivation. It should be not only cover occasional gifts and celebrations, but volunteers should feel that they are an integrated and appreciated part of the overall response system, not just tolerated guests at the table.

Similar challenges have been identified by group B working on Host Nation Support. The focus group identified bottlenecks in information sharing and operational management, highlighting the need for pre-deployment training and exercises. Information management, common operational understanding and sharing of information are crucial elements of Host Nation Support, while a similar structural approach is needed to overcome them.

4. Figure: results of group B. Source: DiMaND D2.3

The third group of the workshop discussed the niches for improvements of municipalities' role. As detailed in D2.3 document, the bottom-up approach at the local level proved to be a good practice. At the same time, networking and the development of pre-existing links with organizations and foreign partners are needed. Harmonization and standardization of protocols could be strengthened, and quality measures could be introduced. Among our analyzed articles, Ishiwatari (2021) discusses similar

challenges, and argues for the formulation of better local plans by municipalities, including the development of guiding policies for local governments by national public bodies (Ishiwatari, 2021).

Stakeholder mapping

To identify the interview participants of our research (introduced by future deliverable D5.3), we implemented a stakeholder mapping exercise based on the results of the literature analysis, the focus group discussions and the authors' expert opinion.

In order to develop a better understanding of the national coordination practices with volunteer and humanitarian organization, we should cover a variety of organizations, including public authorities responsible for the coordination and volunteer-based NGOs offering support in disasters. Applying a standard brainstorming methodology for stakeholder mapping, the following general volunteer actors could be covered by further research.

- volunteer fire brigades
 - volunteer technical rescue organizations
 - search and rescue and special rescue groups
 - water rescue and lifeguard services
 - mountain rescue organizations
 - Red Cross National Societies
 - charities
 - volunteer civil protection associations
 - volunteer community watch organizations (civic policing movements)
 - animal rescue organizations
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References

- Britton, N. R. (1991). Permanent Disaster Volunteers: Where Do They Fit? *Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Quarterly*, 20(4), 395–414. <https://doi.org/10.1177/089976409102000404>
- Cozzolino, A. (2012). Humanitarian Logistics and Supply Chain Management. In *Humanitarian Logistics: Cross-Sector Cooperation in Disaster Relief Management* (pp. 5–16). Springer.
- Eide, A. W., Haugstveit, I. M., Halvorsrud, R., & Borén, M. (2013). Inter-organizational collaboration structures during emergency response: A case study. *ISCRAM 2013 Conference Proceedings - 10th International Conference on Information Systems for Crisis Response and Management, May*, 94–104.
- Fritz, C. E., & Mathewson, J. H. (1957). Convergence Behavior in Disasters. *Committee on Disaster Studies*, 476(9).
- Ishiwatari, M. (2021). Institutional Coordination of Disaster Management: Engaging National and Local Governments in Japan. *Natural Hazards Review*, 22(1), 04020059. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(asce\)nh.1527-6996.0000423](https://doi.org/10.1061/(asce)nh.1527-6996.0000423)
- Kaynak, R., & Tuğer, A. T. (2014). Coordination and Collaboration Functions of Disaster Coordination Centers for Humanitarian Logistics. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 109, 432–437. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.12.486>
- OCHA. (2012). Coordination to Save Lives: History and Emerging Challenges. *Policy and Studies Series*. <https://www.google.com/search?q=Policy+and+Studies+Series+2012+History+and+Emerging+Challenges+COORDINATION+to+SAVE+LIVES&ie=utf-8&oe=utf-8&client=firefox-b-1>
- Salvadó, L. L., Lauras, M., Comes, T., & Van De Walle, B. (2015). Towards more relevant research on Humanitarian Disaster Management coordination. *ISCRAM 2015 Conference Proceedings - 12th International Conference on Information Systems for Crisis Response and Management, 2015-Janua*.
- Stoddard, E. R. (1969). Some Latent Consequences of Bureaucratic Efficiency in Disaster Relief. *Human Organization*, 28(3), 177–189.
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Annex 1 – list of articles analyzed

First author	Year	Title	DOI
Akhtar	2012	Coordination in humanitarian relief chains: chain coordinators	10.1108/20426741211226019
Balick	2010	Coordination in humanitarian relief chains: Practices, challenges and opportunities	10.1016/j.ijpe.2009.09.008
Beck	2014	Temporary, emergent interorganizational collaboration in unexpected circumstances: A study of the Columbia space shuttle response effort	10.1287/orsc.2013.0888
Bharosa	2010	Challenges and obstacles in sharing and coordinating information during multi-agency disaster response: Propositions from field exercises	10.1007/s10796-009-9174-z
Burnside-Lawry	2016	A stakeholder approach to building community resilience: awareness to implementation	10.1108/IJDRBE-07-2013-0028
Carrasco	2016	Disaster Induced Resettlement: Multi-stakeholder Interactions and Decision Making Following Tropical Storm Washi in Cagayan de Oro, Philippines	10.1016/j.sbspro.2016.04.008
Coles	2018	Partner selection in disaster relief: Partnership formation in the presence of incompatible agencies	10.1016/j.ijdr.2017.09.041
Dolinskaya	2011	Decentralized approaches to logistics coordination in humanitarian relief	
Dragaš	2021	Coordination in the Security Sector in Response to Natural Disasters: The Serbia Cases of 2014 Floods and Covid-19	10.11610/isij.4813
Eide	2013	Inter-organizational collaboration structures during emergency response: A case study	
Eide	2014	Key challenges in multi-agency collaboration during large-scale emergency management	
Eller	2015	Voluntary Nonprofit Organizations and Disaster Management: Identifying the Nature of Inter-Sector Coordination and Collaboration in Disaster Service Assistance Provision	10.1002/rhc3.12081
Fisk	2019	Collaboration After Disaster: Explaining Intergovernmental Collaboration During the EPA Gold King Mine and TVA Coal Ash Recoveries	10.1002/rhc3.12156
Fontainha	2020	Stakeholder satisfaction in complex relationships during the disaster response: a structured review and a case study perspective	10.1080/09537287.2020.1834127

Ishiwatari	2021	Institutional Coordination of Disaster Management: Engaging National and Local Governments in Japan	10.1061/(asce)nh.1527-6996.0000423
Kabra	2015	Analyzing drivers and barriers of coordination in humanitarian supply chain management under fuzzy environment	10.1108/BIJ-05-2014-0041
Kaynak	2014	Coordination and Collaboration Functions of Disaster Coordination Centers for Humanitarian Logistics	10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.12.486
Menya	2016	Inter-agency collaboration for fire disaster management in Nairobi City	10.1016/j.jum.2016.08.001
Moshtari	2017	Factors Influencing Interorganizational Collaboration within a Disaster Relief Context	10.1007/s11266-016-9767-3
Pateman	2013	Humanizing humanitarian supply chains : A synthesis of key challenges	10.1016/j.ajsl.2013.05.005
Rongier	2010	Towards a performance measurement system to control disaster response	
Salvadó	2015	Towards more relevant research on Humanitarian Disaster Management coordination	
Scholtens	2008	Controlled collaboration in disaster and crisis management in the Netherlands, history and practice of an overestimated and underestimated concept	10.1111/j.1468-5973.2008.00550.x
Scotter	2012	An examination of interdependencies among major barriers to coordination in disaster response	10.1504/IJEM.2012.051640
Tatham	2017	The humanitarian common logistic operating picture: a solution to the inter-agency coordination challenge	10.1111/disa.12193
Wakolbinger	2013	IT-enabled interorganizational information sharing under co-opetition in disasters: A game-theoretic framework	10.17705/1cais.03305